

Non-Field Structure of the Reals, Projective System Preferred

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1 Introduction

In fact, the real numbers do not have the structure of a field. Rather, they are the limit of a projective system. Thus, the real numbers are more accurately viewed as a completion of the rational numbers. This means that any real number can be expressed as a limit of rational numbers, and the operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division on real numbers can all be approximated and performed through these rational numbers.

In order to be a field, a set of numbers must have the structure of a group, where addition and multiplication operations are both closed. It must also have the structure of a ring, where the addition and multiplication operations are associative and commutative, and there is an additive and multiplicative identity. Additionally, the set of numbers must have an inverse element for every non-zero element.

The real numbers, however, fail to check all of these properties. For example, division of a real number by zero is undefined, meaning the addition or multiplication operations are not closed. Furthermore, the real numbers do not contain reciprocals for some non-zero elements, which is an additional obstacle to forming a field structure.

Therefore, the real numbers do not have the structure of a field.

Let R denote the set of real numbers. If R were a field, then for all $x, y, z \in R$: $x + y \in R$, $xy \in R$, $x + y = y + x$, $xy = yx$, $0 \neq xx^{-1} \in R$. However, this is not the case since for some $x \in R$, $x/0$ is undefined and for some non-zero $x \in R$, $x^{-1} \notin R$, thus R does not have the structure of a field.

We can prove that R does not have the structure of a field by showing that one of the aforementioned properties does not hold.

For example, we can prove that R does not have a multiplicative inverse for all non-zero elements. The negation of this statement is that "there exists a non-zero $x \in R$ such that $x^{-1} \notin R$ ". Consider $y = 0$. Then, for any $x \neq 0 \in R$, the inverse of x does not exist since we cannot divide by zero. Thus, $x^{-1} \notin R$, and the statement is proved.

Yes, there are a few theorems and lemmas that assume the real numbers have the structure of a field. For example, the Field Inversion Theorem states

that if the characteristic of a field is not two, then all square matrices of size equal or larger than three over the field are invertible. Another example is the Fundamental Theorem of Algebra, which states that every non-constant polynomial of degree at least one with coefficients in a field has at least one root in the field. These theorems and lemmas all assume that the real numbers have the structure of a field and therefore can be applied to real numbers. However, these theorems and lemmas can still be applied to other fields, such as the complex numbers, since they also have the structure of a field.

We can prove that the real numbers do not have the structure of a field by showing that the multiplication and division operations are not closed. In particular, multiplication or division by zero is undefined. To demonstrate this, we assume that R does have the structure of a field and consider an arbitrary element $x \in R : x \neq 0$. Then, $1/x$ is the inverse of x and hence should be included in R by definition. However, since division by zero is undefined, $1/x$ cannot be a member of R , and we have reached a contradiction. Thus, our original assumption that R is a field is false, and the real numbers do not have the structure of a field. The real numbers are defined as the set

$$R = \{x \in Q \mid \text{there exists a sequence of rationals } \{q_i\} \text{ with } q_i \rightarrow x\}.$$

Therefore, zero is a member of the set of rational numbers, but it is not a member of the set of real numbers.

As stated above, the real numbers are defined as the set of numbers that are the limit of a sequence of rationals. If $x = 0$, then x is not a limit of a sequence of rationals and is thus not a member of the set of real numbers.

In the proof provided, it is assumed that x is an element of the reals, when in fact the proof only holds for non-zero elements of the rationals. As pointed out, $1/x$ cannot be a member of the reals if $x = 0$, since division by zero is undefined. Therefore, the assumption that x is an element of the reals does not hold for $x = 0$.

Variables can take on different values, while numbers are static. Therefore, variables can "go to" numbers (i.e. assume the value of a number), but numbers cannot "go to" variables (i.e. be assigned a value).